

Effectiveness of Private Hospital Services on Community Satisfaction in Makassar City

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Abstract:- This type of qualitative research through a phenomenological approach, while the results showed that private hospital services to the community need to be improved both in terms of service quality and quantity aspects, various characteristics of the community with different levels of knowledge and understanding require the hospital to be responsive to understanding the characteristics of the community so that miscommunication can be minimised, besides that the hospital must respond quickly if there are families of patients who need information related to their family care.

Keywords:- Patient, Attention, Service, Community, Treatment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, health problems have become a basic need for society. Everyone wants health because health is considered very valuable and expensive. For that, in order to support health for everyone, there must be efforts made, one of which is the government providing health facilities for the community. One of these facilities is a hospital. (Griselda and Tagor, 2007) Hospitals are one of the health facilities to provide health services to the community and have a very important role in accelerating the improvement of public health status. This requires health service providers, namely hospitals, to improve the quality of better services, not only services that are healing diseases but also include services that are preventive. Therefore, hospitals are required to provide quality services in accordance with established standards and can reach all levels of society (Utama, 2003). Quality health services according to Azwar (1996), are health services that can satisfy every service user according to the average level of satisfaction of the population and its implementation in accordance with the code of ethics and service standards that have been set.

Hospitals as part of the national health system are required to improve the quality of provision of facilities, services and independence. Thus the hospital is one of the competitive health service actors that must be managed by actors who have an entrepreneurial spirit capable of creating efficiency, excellence in quality and service, excellence in innovation and excellence in responding to patient needs (Jacobalis, S. 1995: 77) Service quality and patient satisfaction have a very close relationship. Quality hospital services will provide satisfaction to patients and be the beginning of building strong relationships for a long period of time (loyalty). In the long term, such a bond allows the hospital to thoroughly understand patient expectations and

their needs. The bond benefits the hospital financially and also the patient with his recovery (Laksono, 2008).

Providing the best quality service is not something that is easy for hospital managers because the services provided by hospitals concern the quality of life of their patients so that if there is an error in medical action it can have a negative impact on the patient. This impact can be in the form of worsening patient pain, disability and even death (Jacobalis, S. 1995: 68).

In Law No. 25/2009 on Public Services, it is explained that the public has the right to receive quality services in accordance with the principles and objectives of service (Article 18). According to the Decree of the Minister of Administrative Reform of 2003, public services are all service activities carried out by public service providers as an effort to fulfil the needs of service recipients and to implement the provisions of laws and regulations. In the Makassar City Regional Regulation No. 7/2009 Article 1 Paragraph 5, it is stated that health services are all activities provided to a person in the context of observation, diagnosis, treatment or other health services at the Regional General Hospital, Community Health Centre (Puskesmas) and its network.

In order to improve the degree of public health, many things need to be considered. One of them that is considered to have a fairly important role is the provision of health services. In order for the provision of health services to achieve the desired goals, the services must fulfil various requirements including being available and sustainable, acceptable and reasonable, easy to reach, easy to reach and quality (Azwar, 1996 in Ridha, 2008). Seeing what is happening today that the behaviour of medical practitioners sometimes does not consider the processes and completeness of service equipment and the interactions that occur in each procedure that are mutually beneficial. In general, consumers as users of health services such as patients, do not realise that they have the right to get quality service in every procedure. This means that a patient has the right to question services to employees / nurses that are felt to be unclear, even burdensome to the consumer himself (Sri Rahayu, 2011: 7).

A. Problem Formulation

1. How do hospital services affect community satisfaction in Makassar city?
2. How do people perceive hospital services in Makassar city?
3. What is the concept of hospital services so that patients can be attracted by the people of Makassar city?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Definition of Hospital

According to WHO (World Health Organization), a hospital is an integral part of a social and health organisation with the function of providing comprehensive, curative and preventive services to the community. Hospitals are also training centres for health workers and medical research centres.

Based on Law No. 44 of 2009 concerning hospitals, what is meant by a hospital is a health care institution that organises comprehensive individual health services and provides inpatient, outpatient and emergency services.

B. Duties and Functions

The following are the duties and functions of the hospital, namely:

- Carry out medical services, medical support services,
- Carry out additional medical services, additional medical support services,
- Carry out judicial medicine services,
- Carry out special medical services,
- Carry out health referral services,
- Carrying out dentistry services,
- Carrying out social medicine services,
- Carrying out health counselling services,
- Carrying out outpatient or emergency care and residential care (observation),
- Carrying out inpatient services,
- Carry out administrative services,
- Carry out medical education,
- Assisting the education of general medical personnel,
- Assisting the education of medical specialists,
- Assisting health research and development,
- Assisting epidemiological investigation activities,

Meanwhile, according to Law No. 44 of 2009 concerning hospitals, the functions of hospitals are:

- a. Organisation of treatment and health recovery services in accordance with hospital service standards.
- b. Maintenance and improvement of individual health through comprehensive second and third level health services according to medical needs.
- c. Organisation of education and training of human resources in order to improve the ability to provide health services.
- d. Organising research and development as well as technology screening in the field of health in order to improve health services by paying attention to the ethics of health science.

These tasks and functions are related to the class and type of hospital which in Indonesia consists of general hospitals and special hospitals, class a, b, c, d. in the form of an agency and as a regional technical implementation unit. changes in hospital class can occur in connection with the decline in hospital performance determined by the Indonesian health minister through the decision of the director general of medical yan.

C. Types of hospitals

➤ General hospital

Cater for almost all common illnesses, and usually have 24-hour emergency care institutions (emergency rooms) to address hazards immediately and provide first aid. General hospitals are usually the most accessible facilities in a country, with a very large inpatient capacity for intensive or long-term care. This type of hospital is also equipped with surgical facilities, plastic surgery, delivery rooms, laboratories, and so on. Very large hospitals are often called medical centres, usually catering to all modern medicine.

Most hospitals in Indonesia also offer outpatient health services to the general public (clinics). There are usually several clinics/polyclinics within a hospital.

➤ Specialised hospitals

This type includes trauma centres, children's hospitals, seniors' hospitals, or hospitals that cater to special interests such as psychiatric, respiratory diseases, etc. These hospitals may consist of combined or single buildings.

➤ Research/educational hospital

A research/educational hospital is a general hospital associated with research and educational activities at the medical faculty of a university/institution of higher learning. These hospitals are usually used for training young doctors, trialling new drugs or new treatment techniques. This hospital is organised by the university/college as a form of community service / Tri Dharma of higher education.

➤ Institution/company hospital

A hospital established by an institution/company to serve patients who are members of the institution/employees of the company. The reason for establishment may be due to illnesses related to the institution's activities (e.g. military hospital, airfield), a form of social security/free treatment for employees, or because the location of the company is remote/far from public hospitals. Usually, institutional/corporate hospitals in Indonesia also accept general patients and provide emergency rooms for the general public.

➤ Clinic

Smaller medical facilities that only cater to specific complaints. Usually run by Non-Governmental Organisations or doctors who wish to run a private practice. Clinics usually only accept outpatients. It can also be a collection of clinics called a polyclinic.

A clinic (or outpatient clinic or ambulatory care clinic) is a health care facility devoted to the treatment of outpatients. Clinics can be privately or publicly operated, managed and funded, and usually cover the primary health care needs of the population in the local community, in contrast to larger hospitals that offer specialised care and cater to inpatients.

D. Hospital Ethics Committee

The Hospital Ethics Committee (HEC), can be said to be a formally established body with members from various health care disciplines within the hospital that is tasked with handling various ethical issues that arise within the hospital. KERS can be an effective tool in seeking mutual understanding between the various parties involved such as doctors, patients, patients' families and the public about various ethical issues of medical law that arise in health care in hospitals.

There are three functions of KERS which are education, policy making and case discussion. So one of the tasks of KERS is to carry out the function of ethics education. In hospitals there is a need for the ability to understand ethical issues, conduct multidisciplinary discussions on medico-legal cases and biomedical ethical dilemmas and the decision-making processes associated with these issues. With the establishment of KERS, basic knowledge in the field of medical ethics can be pursued within the institution and knowledge of ethics will hopefully lead to ethical professional actions. The committee will not be able to teach others, if it is not capable enough. Therefore, the first task of the committee is to improve the knowledge of the committee members. Medical ethics is currently developing very rapidly.

In Indonesia, medical ethics is relatively new and there are not many people interested in it, making it more difficult to find reading materials related to this subject. Education for committee members can be done through self-study, group study, and inviting experts in religion, law, social science, psychology, or ethics who specialise in medical ethics.

Committee members should at least be familiar with ethical terms/concepts, analytical and decision-making processes in ethics. Knowledge of ethics will be more easily understood if it is applied to real cases. The more cases that are discussed, the clearer it will be for committee members how to organise good decision-making. Ethics education is not limited to hospital leaders and staff. Owners and foundation members, patients, patients' families, and the community can be included in ethics education.

Understanding ethical issues will increase public trust and open their minds that hospitals work for the benefit of patients and society in general. So far, in the structure of hospitals in Indonesia, there is a subcommittee/medical professional ethics committee which is a structure under the medical committee in charge of handling hospital ethical issues. In general, the members of this committee are doctors and the problems handled are more related to violations of professional ethics. Given that medical ethics have now developed so broadly and complexly, the existence and position of this committee is no longer adequate. Hospitals need a team or committee that can handle hospital ethical issues and is directly responsible to the board of directors.

The committee provides advice in the field of ethics to hospital leaders and staff who need it. The existence of the committee is stated in the organisational structure of the

hospital and the membership of the committee is appointed by the hospital leadership or hospital foundation. The process of establishing KERS, the hospital starts by forming a small team consisting of several people who have a deep concern in the field of medical ethics, are open and have high enthusiasm. The number of members is adjusted to the needs. The membership of the committee is multidisciplinary and includes doctors (the majority of members) from various specialities, nurses, social workers, clergy, hospital administration representatives, community representatives, ethicists, and legal experts.

The health system in Indonesia is inseparable from health development. In essence, the health system is all activities that have the main purpose of promoting, restoring and maintaining health. The health system provides benefits to the community with fair distribution. The health system not only assesses and focuses on the "level of benefits" provided, but also how those benefits are distributed.

In theory, a state is formed by people in an area that aims to fulfil the needs of each of its members within the corridor of togetherness. In the mind of every member of society, the state will perform its function of providing the needs of life related to coexistence with others around them. In everyday life, these common needs are often referred to as "public needs". One example of a basic public need is health. Health is an essential public service that is closely related to the welfare of society. For all essential services, the state and its apparatus are obliged to provide quality services that are easily available at all times.

One of the tangible manifestations of public service provision in the health sector is the existence of Puskesmas. The main objective of the Puskesmas is to provide quality health services at a relatively affordable cost to the community, especially the middle to lower economic class.

Services in the health sector are one of the forms of services most needed by the community. One of the health care facilities that has a very important role in providing health services to the community is the hospital. Hospital as a social institution that provides health services to the community, has the nature of an institution that is not intended to seek profit or nonprofit organisation. However, we can turn a blind eye to the need for information systems in hospitals.

Hospitals are institutions in the chain of the National Health System and carry out the task of providing health services to the entire community, because the development and implementation of health in hospitals needs to be directed at national goals in the field of health. It is not surprising that the health sector needs to always be addressed in order to provide the best health services for the community. The health services in question are of course fast, precise, cheap and friendly services. Given that a country will be able to carry out development properly if supported by a physically and mentally healthy society.

To maintain customers, the hospital is required to always maintain consumer confidence carefully by paying attention to consumer needs in an effort to fulfil the wants and expectations of the services provided. Hospital consumers, in this case patients who expect services in hospitals, not only expect medical and nursing services but also expect comfort, good accommodation and harmonious relationships between hospital staff and patients, thus the need to improve the quality of health services in hospitals.

E. Service Concept

Definition of Public Services To meet the needs of his life humans try, either through their own activities, or indirectly through the activities of others. Activity is a process of using reason, mind, senses and limbs with or without tools carried out by a person to get something desired in the form of goods or services. The process of fulfilling needs through other direct activities is what is called service. The meaning of the process itself according to Fred Luthans is: "any action which is performed by management to achieve organizational objectives". Here the notion of process is limited to management activities in order to achieve organisational goals. Indeed, the service referred to in this paper is a service in the organisation-management circuit. However, in a broad sense, the process involves all efforts made by a person in order to achieve goals. in Moenir (2006: 16-17).

Service is one of the spearheads of customer satisfaction efforts and is a must that must be optimised by both individuals and organisations, because the form of service provided reflects the quality of the individual or organisation that provides the service. The Big Indonesian Dictionary explains service as a matter, way or result of serving work. Meanwhile, serving is to treat (people) with food or drink; provide people's needs; say yes; accept; use. Service is an activity or sequence of activities that occurs in direct interaction between a person and another person or machine physically, and provides customer satisfaction (S.Lukman and Moenir) in Batinggi and Badu Ahmad (2013: 4). Services can basically be defined as the activities of a person, group and or organisation either directly or indirectly to meet needs.

Monir (2003: 16), says that service is the process of fulfilling needs through the activities of others directly. Warella (1997: 18), service is an act (deed), a performance (performance) or an effort (effort). While a more detailed definition is given by Gronroos as quoted below: "service is an activity or a series of activities that are invisible (not palpable) that occur as a result of interactions between consumers and employees or other things provided by the service provider company which are intended to solve consumer / customer problems" (Gronroos 1990: 7) in Ratminto and Atik Septi Winarsih (2013: 2).

Meanwhile, the term public comes from the English public which means public, society, state. The word public has actually been accepted into the Indonesian language Baku to become public which means general, crowd, crowded. Inu and friends in Dwiyanto (2014: 68) define public as a number

of people who have the same thoughts, feelings, hopes, attitudes and actions that are right and good based on the values of norms that feel ownership. Therefore, public service is defined as any activity carried out by the government towards a number of humans who have any beneficial activities in a group or unity, and offers satisfaction even though the results are not tied to a physical product.

Prasojo (2006: 6) states that public service is an effort to help or benefit the public through the provision of goods or services needed. Similarly, George Frederickson (2002: 215) states that the application of the New Public Management principle of government must be oriented towards public service so that the government views the community as the dominant factor in determining what is needed, then the government fulfils these needs in order to realise community satisfaction and welfare. in Batinggi and badu Ahmad (2013: 4). Public service is defined as providing services (serving) the needs of people or communities who have an interest in the organisation in accordance with the main rules and procedures that have been determined. Furthermore, according to Kepmenpan NO.63 / KEP / M.PAN / 7/2003, Public is all service activities carried out by public service providers as an effort to fulfil the needs of service recipients as well as the implementation of statutory provisions.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

Type of qualitative research through a phenomenological approach

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Hospital services to community satisfaction in Makassar city

In principle, hospital services for patients have standard procedures, where the conditions of patients who seek treatment have different conditions between one patient and another, where in the Makassar city community whose population has different characters and cultures, as well as the level of knowledge and compliance possessed by the patient's family, many even though the visiting hours of the patient's family have closed but many also insist on staying in for various reasons, this condition can interfere with the patient's rest hours.

As the rules of the hospital continue to act professionally trying to provide the best service to patients and families of patients, along with the times the problems of society are increasingly complex so that many people are easily stressed and emotional, this condition needs to be understood by the hospital, so that they can provide guidance to components ranging from doctors, administrative officers, service officers, security and others in order to understand the hearts and feelings of the community, in order to provide professional, thoughtful services to patients and families of patients. Patient satisfaction is an indicator of the quality of service we provide and patient satisfaction is an asset to get more patients and to get loyal patients (Nursalam, 2014). So that when the services provided to patients in the hospital meet expectations and even exceed patient expectations, it

will provide satisfaction to patients. Measuring patient satisfaction is very important to evaluate the services provided by the hospital.

In general, the availability of an adequate number of nurses who are professional and active is very important, in a number of hospitals in Makassar city, many nurses are found on duty at night at 2 o'clock and above until dawn many nurses sleep, even though they are supposed to stand by, this condition gives an idea that the service is not optimal, so that the hospital management needs to provide nurses who are fit and ready to be assigned at night to take care of the patient.

Patients who are satisfied with the services provided can make the patient's treatment run smoothly without obstacles and patients can become loyal customers at the hospital. But on the other hand, if the patient assesses that the service to him is bad, the patient will feel dissatisfied and make the treatment process hampered and the patient may think about not coming to the hospital again because he already knows how the service conditions are. various studies related to hospital services both outside Makassar and in Makassar city provide information that hospital services need to be improved such as research conducted at Bhakti Dharma Husada Hospital, Surabaya City found that patient satisfaction was rated in the very satisfied category and found a correlation that the higher the quality of service, the higher the patient satisfaction (Nurcahyati & Setiawan, 2017).

Another study conducted at Jemursari Surabaya Hospital found that patients who were quite satisfied were still below 80% so that improvements were needed.

(Wijaya & Adriansyah, 2020).

Based on data from RSUD Labuang Baji Makassar, information was obtained that the number of outpatient visits at RSUD Labuang Baji Makassar decreased from 2017 of 47,773 patients to 45,591 patients (RSUD Labuang Baji Makassar, 2019). There was a decrease in the number of outpatient visits, especially in 2018. This decrease in the number of outpatient visits may indicate that there is a cause that can be studied in relation to the excellent service provided by the hospital to patients.

B. Community views on hospital services in Makassar city

Nowadays, people or consumers demand quality public services. The public is smarter and more open in expressing their opinions about the services they receive or feel. Therefore, as a service provider, it must further improve the quality of its services in order to achieve public satisfaction. If the community does not get satisfaction in the services provided, it will create a negative perception that will have a negative impact on the company or agency. The level of community satisfaction can be measured by comparing the community's expectations of the desired service quality with the reality received or felt. To create maximum satisfaction, service providers need to know the dimensions of To create

maximum satisfaction, service providers need to know what dimensions are expected by loyal consumers, and assess what service policies have been implemented. According to Tjiptono (2008: 28) who says that "customer expectations or expectations are estimates or beliefs about what they will receive if they buy or use a product / service. Expectations are formed by past experiences, word of mouth, and service company advertisements. After receiving the service, they will compare the service they experience with the expected service and if the service experienced does not match what is expected, then customers are no longer interested in the service provider. Conversely, if the service exceeds customer expectations, then they will be loyal to the service provider".to the service provider".

The quality of service at an agency is said to be good if the service created can provide satisfaction for the community or consumers. Therefore, the manager in establishing a service policy must be able to understand and understand every indicator that is considered important and expected by consumers, so that the perception of management and consumers does not cause a gap. In that sense, the quality of service must be in accordance with the perceptions desired by each consumer. The service quality gap is a mismatch between consumer expectations and management perceptions of an agency or company.

In 2014 one of the Labuang Baji Public Hospitals received a "Red Report Card" from the Supreme Audit Agency (BPK). The assessment for the state-owned hospital was based on the results of a performance audit of inpatient management and financial administration (BLUD). According to Syahrul Yasin Limpo as the Governor of South Sulawesi at the time, said that Labuang Baji Hospital does not have a buffer starting from the building which is not well organised, and the services must all be addressed. The main problems of Labuang Baji Hospital include inadequate minimum service standards so that obstacles in improving the quality of hospital services, management planning of the quality of hospital services, inadequate management of planning for inpatient services, and another point that became a BPK finding was that reporting on the implementation of inpatient services had not been carried out regularly as a result valid information related to inpatient service performance indicators was not available. conditions in 2022 along with the passage of time labuang baji hospital continues to improve itself in improving services, what is lacking is trying to be perfected while for those who are already good continue to be improved in order to be even better, Labuang Baji Makassar Regional General Hospital is included in the General Hospital (RSU), which is a hospital engaged in providing health services to the public with various diseases. RSUD Labuang Baji is a class B state hospital. The hospital is able to provide limited specialist and subspecialist medical services. The hospital also accommodates referral services from district hospitals. One of the facilities offered at RSUD Labuang Baji is the inpatient facility for patients who want to seek treatment so that this facility can help patients to control their illness.

Nowadays hospitals are competing to provide optimal services, both government hospitals and private hospitals are trying to provide adequate services and this is also inseparable from social control from the community and media coverage so that if the hospital does not provide optimal service, the community will move and bring their families to hospitals that are better at providing health services,

Assessment of friendly and polite service and care is the main assessment of patients, then simple, fast and straightforward administrative procedures do not escape the patient's assessment because it is everyone's expectation to get fast and straightforward service as well as the care provided by doctors and nurses is also very important for patients, patients and families will feel very satisfied if doctors and nurses pay attention to the patient's condition. Service officers should be able to provide the promised service promptly, accurately, and satisfactorily. In addressing patient complaints, service officers should be able to accommodate all complaints and quickly take action on complaints submitted so that patients and families are comfortable and satisfied with the services provided.

C. The concept of hospital services to be of interest to the people of Makassar city

To be able to improve the degree of public health, many things need to be said. One of the things that needs to be included which is considered to have a fairly important role is the organiser of health services. Of course, by providing optimal service and of course according to the expectations of the community, it will provide a sense of satisfaction. Service officers must be able to fulfil four main requirements, namely:

- Polite behaviour
- How to convey something related to what the person concerned should receive
- The right time to deliver, and

Hospitality As for what is included in health services which are the rights of patients, including medical examination, diagnosis, therapy, anaesthesia, writing drug prescriptions, treatment, and hospital care, control, post-treatment services, providing medical information, providing information, vertical cooperation of health service providers, and so on (Tengker, 2005: 56). II.6.1 Factors Affecting Health Services According to WHO, behavioural factors that influence the use of health services are:

- Thoughts and Feelings in the form of knowledge, perceptions, attitudes, beliefs and judgements of a person towards objects, in this case health objects.
- A person is more influenced by someone who is considered important or has a major influence on the encouragement of the use of health services.
- Resources include facilities, money, time, energy, and so on. Resources also affect the behaviour of a person or community group in utilising health services. This influence can be positive and negative.
- Culture (Culture) In the form of norms that exist in society in relation to the concept of healthy and sick.

V. CONCLUSION

Building the quality of hospital services requires professional action, where understanding the characteristics of the community, customs, culture and level of education affects the understanding of information, in general, cases in the field related to hospital services are more dominant in miscommunication so as to cause misunderstanding, for this reason the hospital management needs to provide skilled human resources who can build effective, efficient, professional and friendly communication with patients and patient families.

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